

Speculative Cancer Cure

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Answer: it's tritium (tritiated water), injected twice a week into the cancer site, with occasional small amounts concentrated phosphoric acid to dissolve the 'hard nucleus' that forms from the process.

Discussion

I have known about jawbone cancer from radium for a long time. I used to be a radiation researcher in another field – dark matter detection – and would often look up the effects of all the various radioactive isotopes I would study. Now radium is an interesting case. In the early 20th century the public – particularly the America public – were clearly fascinated by radiation, and believed that ingesting as much as possible would lead to a long and healthy life. Marie Curie's death from a blood disorder related to decades of work with radioactive materials aside, looking back, it seems that the general public came to view all radiation as simply 'good', and wanted to drink it. So was born the 'radium water' craze, that just about started just after the end of World War 1 and ending at the start of the great depression. The main product of this period was Radithor – brand-named radium water – that sold 400,000 bottles. While only a few deaths were clearly, directly linked to Radithor – it is clear that these were all cancer deaths – and jaw-bone cancer.

Now, why jawbone cancer? I think the answer is simple. Radium is in the same column of the periodic table as calcium, and so like all heavy metals in the body, tends to replace the lighter metal that has the closest chemical reactivity profile. Incidentally, it seems to me a general rule with heavy metal poisoning, that the heavy metal tends to replace the element that is 'lighter' but has a very similar chemistry profile (oxidation states and so on). I speculate that this is because cells actually prefer the heavier (rarer) metal as it makes it easier for the rest of the cell to assemble 'around' the rare ion – though this makes the cell super-active and thus puts undue strain on the rest of the body, hence poisoning. Back to radium, well as soon as one drinks radium water (Radithor), the first bone sites are in the jaw, and so the radium in the radithor tends to switch out with the calcium in the jaw bones.

Okay, from there, why cancer? Again I think the answer is simple – using well known radioactive decay mechanics and my 25 year old GCSE B grade Biology. Basically it is that radium is an alpha decay, which means a relatively fast moving brick of a helium nucleus is emitted during the radium decay, which should in turn completely 'mush up' the cell that

the radium finds itself in. Now the path length of the alpha (how far it travels) is of the order 10s of micrometers in water (roughly cell consistency, even bone), and that is roughly the same size as the various kinds of cell in the body. This means that only one or a very small number of cells are completely shredded internally by this fast moving brick of an alpha (helium nucleus) before stopping. Again using my GCSE B grade biology – the cell becomes goopy and jelly like, and so looks to expand and multiply until it hits a hard wall it cannot overcome in-order to stabilise: this is cancer.

Right, so if that is cancer – hmm, maybe, but how does that help. First, it means I can tell you right now, how to get cancer, at home, if you so desire. All you need to do is collect hundreds of wrist watches with glowing dials. Then, using a needle, you can scratch off the green-glow into a small pot from each of the dials, until you have sufficient (so a few hundred). Then, you can use any acid, let us say sulphuric acid, to dissolve the radium from the dial paint, pour the solution through a hard paper filter to remove the last pieces of scraped off paint, and you now have a relatively concentrated amount of (acidized) radium, with which you can give yourself jawbone cancer, if you so desire.

Again, why does this help – it is because I believe I have demonstrated a method to medical personnel that they were not aware of – which they too I believe will agree will allow a person to be 'given' cancer in a reliable fashion. This is useful for testing a cure, below.

So, a cure, why do I believe it is tritium. My reasoning is as follows: when tritium decays, it decays via a beta decay – producing a fast, lance-like electron that travels a millimetre or a few (so a path of hundreds of cells long before scattering). Unlike an alpha decay which as mentioned is like a fast brick able to destroy and gut the innards of a single or a few cells, a beta decay like tritium is more like a rail gun, making a tiny line-hole through hundreds of cells in a (near) straight line row from the decay origin. Again, with my 25 years old GCSE B Grade Biology, I would then expect these cells to toughen to prevent leakage, basically hardening – becoming more bone like, seeking to acquire calcium, to resist the effects of future piercing events. Now, if tritium were thus injected into the centre of a cancer site, I would expect it to quite rapidly (days to weeks) form a hard 'nucleus' due to the effects of this beta radiation – while the overall cancer shrinks from this hardening. Now removing this nucleus is quite dangerous, as it still risks spreading the cancer, so I would in this case recommend injecting it with phosphoric acid – famously in Coca Cola capable of dissolving teeth (but only in extremely high concentrations of course).

Now the question I imagine would me on the minds of medical personnel reading this are – what dosage? - I don't know – and why does the tritium need twice a week when it has a half life of 10 years? – it is because tritiated water like all water in the body washes out very quickly if it is the 'new' water to the body rather than fixed in cell structures. At any rate one can use a Geiger counter on evacuated body fluids (or blood if required) to determine the

overall blood-decay rate of the tritium. A similar question with the phosphoric acid – I don't know – I just know this to be a safe way to dissolve (inert-ish) tumors given the 6 litres to 8 litres of coca cola I drink every day, with the main side effect being a bit tubby.

Right to anyone reading this far – why did I go so far into showing how to get the cause of cancer in a 'make it at home' fashion (radium) and not bother at all with the cure (tritium) - which you can also make at home from fire-exit signs, a lighter, and a hammer. The main reason is that medical doctors have always had 'unofficial', quasi-legal ways of experimenting (on themselves and each-other) in order to determine the cure of 'something'. In the case of cancer the problem they have had has NOT been choices in cure of which tritium is just one speculative candidate ultimately, but on a reliable 'make it at home' cause.

Okay, I will leave you dear reader with 'I believe the cure for HIV is an injection of medical doctor's blood because of their excellent immune systems from being around sick and old people'.

Per guidelines, this work is published under my 'passport name' (deadname). My real name is Lucy Mavek Trump; we all get to choose our own names after transitioning, and this is mine.

This work is dedicated to those truly perfect beings, Belle-Delphine